

Organization of a project management system for the construction of main gas networks using communication and information technologies

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The construction of main pipelines is a long and painstaking work, and main pipelines are used as a main transportation system in many industries, especially in the field of gas transportation. Based on the wisdom of our republic, much attention is now being paid to this area of construction.

In 2020, according to the results of a joint study by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the Asian Development Bank, the Republic of Uzbekistan ranks 17th in terms of natural gas reserves*. Natural gas resources, which make up a significant part of the economy of the republic, are exported from the territory of Uzbekistan to Russia and China, extracted and used for the needs of the population.

Main gas pipelines are certainly used to deliver natural gas, and this is an important aspect as an integral part of the energy system. In our Republic, UZTRANSGAZ JSC, a separate authority exercising control over the organization and use of the gas transmission system and facilities, was created for the construction, operation and maintenance of gas transmission networks. The main objective of the company is the supply of produced and processed natural gas reserves to wholesale and retail distributors. Before talking about the system, let's talk a little about information about main gas pipelines, their construction and use.

A gas pipeline is an engineering structure designed to transport natural gas, through which natural gas is delivered under a certain pressure. Gas pipelines are divided into main and

distribution gas pipeline networks.

Main gas pipelines are a network of pipelines designed to transport natural gas over relatively long distances. Compressor stations (devices for maintaining gas pressure in a certain order) are built to maintain constant pressure in the main gas pipeline and help control gas pressure during transportation. At the last point of the main gas pipelines, gas distribution stations are being built, which serve to reduce the gas pressure to the minimum level for the consumer.

Main gas pipelines, depending on pressure, are divided into several types:

Main gas

First class - pressure from 2.5 to 10 MPa

Second class - pressure from 1.2 to 2.5 MPa

Distributor

High pressure

Category 1 - from 0.6 to 1.2 MPa

Category 2 - pressure from 0.3 to 0.6 MPa

Medium pressure - from 0.005 to 0.3 MPa pressure

Low pressure - up to 0.005 MPa

3 different types according to mechanism design

1. Aboveground gas pipelines
2. Underground gas pipelines
3. Divided into underwater gas pipelines

Why are main gas pipelines needed? Since gas fields are remote from the main centers of gas consumption and industrial zones, the produced gas is delivered to consumers through these pipelines. Therefore, the gas pipeline has been and remains the most important element of the system. If we imagine the modern gas system as a tree with roots, then its roots are natural gas wells, and we can see gas pipelines as its trunk. Gas flows through this body at a speed of tens of

kilometers per hour under a pressure of hundreds of atmospheres.

The origin of main gas networks dates back to ancient China. The use of gas began in the II-III centuries. BC, primarily as a source of lighting and heat. The ancient Chinese used evaporation technology to extract salt from salt water, in which gas was delivered through bamboo pipes in gas fields. Bamboo pipes were glued together, and the gas was supplied by natural pressure in the mine. In the first half of the 19th century, the use of natural gas for heating began in Europe, and main gas pipelines were built.

The construction and operation of gas pipelines is a high-cost project, and their construction requires high precision and perfection of technological processes. The processes of managing such projects are now becoming relatively simple, and the main reason for this is the introduction of information communication systems in project management. Switching networks are used as a means of connecting gasification processes in the form of a network and phased implementation, with the help of modern switching devices, work processes are greatly simplified and continuous organization of links between technological processes is ensured.

(* source <https://ru.wikipedia.org>)